

Direct Power Control of the Active Filter Powered by a Solar System for Harmonic Compensation¹

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Abstract

The quality of electrical energy is now a major issue in distribution systems, particularly because of the proliferation of non-linear loads connected to the network. These loads, such as rectifiers, variable speed drives or switch-mode power supplies, introduce disturbances in the form of current and voltage harmonics. These harmonic components cause significant distortion of the sinusoidal signal, leading to a deterioration in the quality of the power supplied. In contrast to passive filters, active power filters are an effective and flexible solution for compensating for harmonics. Active power filters are capable of injecting dynamic compensation currents adapted to the disturbances present, thus improving the quality of the current wave injected into the network. With this in mind, this paper proposes to compensate for harmonics by using an active filter powered by a renewable energy source, in this case a photovoltaic panel. In order to optimise the system's performance, a direct power control is provided to drive the active filter. The entire system was modelled and simulated using Matlab/Simulink. The results obtained confirm the relevance of the proposed solution, with a clear improvement in the quality of the power injected into the network, in particular by reducing the rate of harmonic distortion. This work highlights the growing interest in combining renewable energy technologies and advanced control techniques to meet the challenges of power quality in modern networks.

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Submitted: 05 April 2025 / Published online: 11 June 2025
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Keywords

PV, MPPT, Direct Power Control, Non-linear load, Active filter, Harmonic.

Introduction

Nowadays, it is commonplace to find that electrical installations, whether domestic, industrial or tertiary, incorporate a large number of non-linear loads connected to the distribution network. These loads, such as electronic equipment, variable speed drives, rectifiers and switch-mode power supplies, have become essential to our modern lifestyles. They are so ubiquitous in everyday and industrial applications that it is difficult, if not impossible, to do without them [1]. However, because of their non-linear nature, these loads are responsible for generating current harmonics, which propagate through the electrical network [2, 3]. These undesirable frequency components disrupt the ideal sinusoidal shape of the current and voltage, resulting in a significant deterioration in the quality of the electrical energy. This phenomenon can cause a variety of malfunctions in installations, including overheating of transformers and equipment, nuisance tripping of protection devices, additional line losses, shortened life expectancy of sensitive equipment and desynchronization of control systems. These harmful effects compromise the stability and efficiency of electrical installations for both industrial and residential users [4]. Faced with the growing problem of the degradation of electrical power quality due to the proliferation of non-linear loads, several solutions have been studied and implemented over the years [5-8]. Among these, the use of active power filters (APFs) has emerged as one of the most effective and promising approaches. Unlike passive filters, which are limited by their resonance and frequency rigidity, active filters offer dynamic, selective and adaptive compensation [9, 10].

With their ability to inject a compensating current that is equal and opposite to the harmonics generated by the disturbing loads, APFs can restore a virtually sinusoidal waveform to the current upstream of the connection point, thereby considerably improving power quality in electrical installations. The efficiency of active filters depends largely on the control algorithms that drive them. Advanced strategies such as direct power control (DPC) and others can optimise filter responsiveness, stability and accuracy in variable load environments [11-13]. These techniques not only provide efficient harmonic compensation, but also reactive power regulation and load balancing, contributing to grid stability. Today more than ever, in a global context marked by energy transition, the search for solutions to improve power quality remains a priority. The growing integration of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, accentuates the need to maintain optimum power quality. Although these sources are clean and sustainable, they introduce new production dynamics that are often variable and difficult to control, and can compromise grid stability. This is why active filters, particularly when fed by these renewable sources, represent a particularly relevant synergy. In addition, the policies of many countries are strongly encouraging the adoption of green energies, making the search for intelligent, integrated solutions for managing the quality of electrical energy all the more topical and strategic [14, 15]. It is in this context that we propose the application of DPC to control the filter fed by a photovoltaic source. DPC is based on a simple but effective principle: direct control of the active (P) and reactive (Q) powers exchanged between the active filter and the grid, without using a cascade control loop or a conventional pulse width modulator (PWM). It uses a switching table and information from the flow and

instantaneous power analysis to determine the optimum state of the inverter at each instant. This method provides rapid harmonic reduction, improved power factor and good dynamic response, making it a particularly suitable strategy for applications requiring fast and accurate control, such as harmonic compensation [16, 17]. This approach involves powering the active filter from a photovoltaic solar panel, thus combining the advantages of renewable energies and advanced control techniques. In order to validate the effectiveness of the proposed solution, we will carry out an in-depth analysis of the rate of harmonic distortion of the current injected into the grid, under different operating conditions of the installation. This study will demonstrate the robustness and performance of the DPC control and the management of active and reactive power, while highlighting the benefits of integrating renewable energies into power compensation devices to improve the quality of electrical energy. The harmonic and reactive currents generated by the non-linear loads connected to the PCC cause disturbances and therefore deteriorate the quality of power on the electricity distribution networks. In this work a control algorithm called DPC is developed for its main advantages.

In addition, to extract maximum power (MPPT) from the PV modules, a PSO algorithm is inserted at the DC bus control level to generate an optimal voltage reference. The entire structure is implemented in MatLab/Simulink and simulation results are presented and analysed.

2. Chain structure and modelling

The structure of the chain considered and proposed in this work is represented by the block diagram in Figure 1. It consists of the connection of a non-linear load (NL Load) to the three-phase alternating distribution network (AC Grid). It is equipped with power active filter (FAP: three-phase inverter) fed by a boost converter (DC converter) connected at its input to a photovoltaic solar system (GPV: photovoltaic generator). The DC converter is controlled by MPPT, while the FAP uses direct power control to monitor the inverter's input voltage and active and reactive power

Fig 1. Schema of the chain structure

2.1. Modelling the photovoltaic generator (module)

A photovoltaic generator converts light energy from the sun directly into electrical energy using the

photovoltaic effect. It consists of solar panels (or photovoltaic modules) made up of photovoltaic cells [18]. The equivalent electrical circuit of a PV module is shown in Figure 2.

Fig 2. The equivalent circuit for a solar module

It can be seen that the PV module combines several inserted series connected at several periods or in parallel, and the output current can be expressed as [19]:

$$I_p = N_p \cdot I_{ph} - N_p I_d \left(e^{\left(\frac{V + I R_s \cdot \frac{N_s}{N_p}}{a N_s V_t} \right)} - 1 \right) - \frac{V + I R_s \cdot \frac{N_s}{N_p}}{R_{sh} \cdot \frac{N_s}{N_p}} \quad (1)$$

Where N_s and N_p represent the number of cells connected in series or parallel respectively.

In this work, we use the TP140SBZ solar panel whose characteristics are given in Table 1. The static characteristics of current and power as a function of voltage ($I_{pv}=f(V_{pv})$ and $P_{pv}=f(V_{pv})$), under different irradiation levels, are shown in Figure 3.

Table 1. Array data

Parallel strings	2
Series-connected modules	12
Maximum of Power (W)	139,6944
Cells per module	36
Open circuit voltage (V)	22,25
Short-circuit current (A)	6,36
Voltage at the peak power point (V)	17,44
Current at the peak power point (A)	8,01

Fig 3. Characteristics $I_{pv}=f(V_{pv})$ and $P_{pv}=f(V_{pv})$

It can be seen that the maximum power that can be delivered by the GPV depends significantly on the level of irradiation. As a result, MPPT control is required to operate the system optimally (maximum power extraction) whatever the level of irradiation.

2.2. BOOST Chopper

A boost chopper is a DC-DC (direct current to direct current) converter used to raise the input voltage to an output voltage higher than that applied to its input. Its electrical circuit is illustrated in Figure 4.

Fig 4. BOOST scheme

It consists essentially of an inductor (L), a MOSFET transistor (K), a diode (D) and output capacitors (C). There are two operating phases:

- Conduction phase (K closed): the current flows through the source and the inductor, the energy is stored in the inductor in the form of a magnetic field and the diode is blocked (no current to the load).
- The current flows through the diode to the load and the output voltage is higher than the input voltage.

The dynamic behaviour of the boost converter can be described using state equations derived from its operation in two modes: 'switch closed' (ON) and 'switch open' (OFF). When the switch is closed, the inductor stores energy; when it is open, this energy is transferred to the load via the diode. The voltage across the capacitor and the current through the inductor can be modelled as follows [20, 21].

$$\frac{dV_{DC}}{dt} = \frac{i_L(1-d) - I_{DC}}{C_{out}} \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dI_{DC}}{dt} = \frac{V_{DC}(1-d) - V_{A out}}{L} \quad (3)$$

Assuming steady-state operation, ideal switching (no losses) and perfect components, the output voltage (V_{out}) as a function of the input voltage (V_{in}) is given by the relationship below:

$$V_{out} = \frac{V_{in}}{1-D} \quad (4)$$

Where, V_{in} : input voltage; V_{out} : output voltage; D: duty cycle equal between 0 and 1.

2.3. Active filter

This work deals with a parallel active filter (PAF) designed to compensate for the harmonic currents generated by the connected non-linear load. The FAP consists of a voltage inverter and an inductive output filter, connected in parallel at the common connection point. It is connected in parallel to the common connection point. This filter behaves like a controllable harmonic current source, injecting a current equal to that absorbed by the non-linear load, but in phase opposition to it, so that the source

current after compensation is sinusoidal and in phase with the corresponding voltage [22]. The SAPF is a voltage structure connected in parallel to the grid. It is essentially made up of two parts, a power part and a control part, [20] as shown in figure 5.

Fig 5. Structure of a parallel filter

2.4. Modeling of the voltage source inverter

Vector PWM control involves placing the control vector in the two-phase reference frame obtained by using the Clarke transform. The possible switches can be coded on three states (S_a , S_b , S_c) which gives eight possible vectors, two of which are zero (V_0 and V_7).

Table 2 .VSI output generated voltages

Vector Number	Switch state			Voltage output		
	Sa	Sb	Sc	Va	Vb	Vc
1	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	1	-V	-V	-V
3	0	1	0	-V	2V	-V
4	0	1	1	-2V	V	V
5	1	0	0	2V	-V	-V
6	1	0	1	V	2V	V
7	1	1	0	V	V	V
8	1	1	1	0	0	0

Where, $V = V_{dc}/3$

3. Control strategies

In modern electrical distribution systems integrating renewable energy sources and also non-linear loads, maintaining stable and efficient operation requires the implementation of advanced and effective control strategies. Indeed, the variability of renewable resources, combined with the increasing complexity of networks, requires control techniques capable of responding in real time to fluctuations in load and generation. In this work, we propose the use of the PSO (Particle Swarm Optimization) method to control the chopper associated with the photovoltaic generator, while direct power control is applied to the active filter. This dual approach aims to optimise the overall operation of the system, in particular by: significantly reducing the rate of THD, ensuring optimum injection of the active power produced by the photovoltaic field, effectively managing exchanges of reactive power with the grid. Thus, the joint

use of these control strategies helps to improve the quality of the electrical energy injected while enhancing the stability and reliability of the distribution system.

3.1 Method Particle Swarm Optimization

According to the figure illustrating the characteristics of the photovoltaic panel, the maximum power point (MPPT - Maximum Power Point Tracking) that a photovoltaic generator (GPV) can develop is highly dependent on climatic conditions, and more specifically on the level of solar irradiation. Any variation in irradiation or temperature has a direct impact on the panel's output voltage and current, altering the optimum operating point. Consequently, in order to guarantee maximum extraction of the available power whatever the weather conditions, several optimisation algorithms have been developed and integrated into photovoltaic systems [23-24]. Among the most commonly used are : The P&O (Perturb and Observe) algorithm, which adjusts the operating point by periodically perturbing the voltage or current and observing the effect on power, the Incremental Conductance (IncCond) algorithm, based on the calculation of the derivative of power with respect to voltage, which allows more accurate monitoring of the MPP, artificial intelligence-based and metaheuristic methods [25].

In this work, we use the PSO (Particle Swarm Optimization) method [26, 27] to track the maximum power point (MPPT) of the photovoltaic system. PSO is an optimisation technique inspired by the collective behaviour of swarms, particularly that of birds or schools of fish in search of food. Its principle is based on a population of particles (candidate solutions) moving through the search space. Each particle adjusts its position according to its personal experience (best position reached) and that of its neighbours (best known overall position), with the aim of converging towards the optimal solution. Figure.6 presented the algorithm of the PSO method which is applied in the photovoltaic system to optimize the output power in the panels. The step to solve the problem by PSO can be found in [28].

Fig 6. PSO algorithm

3.2. Direct Power control

DPC is a direct control method that allows direct control of the instantaneous power injected by the filter without going through a current regulation loop. The proposed DPC control combines: a PI regulator for regulating the DC bus voltage and a direct control strategy, allowing the appropriate voltage vector to be selected from the converter without any modulation techniques. The basic concept is to select the appropriate switching states from a switching table based on the errors, which are limited by a hysteresis band, present in the active and reactive powers, as illustrated in Figure 7 [20].

Active power P is defined as the scalar product of voltage and current components, while reactive power Q is expressed as the vector product of same components.

$$\begin{cases} P = V_{\alpha}I_{\alpha} + V_{\beta}I_{\beta} \\ Q = V_{\alpha}I_{\beta} - V_{\beta}I_{\alpha} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where, V_{α} , I_{α} , V_{β} , and I_{β} represent the Clarke components of the instantaneous values of three-phase voltages and currents.

The errors in active power (dP) and reactive power (dQ) are given by the following expressions [15]:

$$dP = P_{ref} - P \quad (6)$$

$$dQ = Q_{ref} - Q \quad (7)$$

Where P_{ref} represents the desired active of power, P the actual active of power, Q_{ref} desired reactive power, and Q the actual reactive power. Moreover, the angular of position θ_n for the grid voltage vector is determined using the following formula:

$$\theta_n = \arctan\left(\frac{V_{\alpha}}{V_{\beta}}\right) \quad (8)$$

Where, in the case of field division into 12 sectors as shown in the figure, we have:

$$\frac{\pi}{6}(n - 2) \leq (\theta_n - 1) \leq \frac{\pi}{6}(n - 1) \quad (9)$$

$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, 12$.

Fig 7. Possible sectors selector

Using the error signals and the angular position, a switching table is constructed, storing all the switching states dP and dQ of the converter. These states take the value "1" to indicate an increase in the controlled variable (P or Q) and "0" to indicate a decrease. The dual-level hysteresis regulators for

instantaneous active and reactive power can be described as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If, } P_{ref} - P \geq HB P \quad dP = 1 \\ \text{If, } P_{ref} - P < HB P \quad dP = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The same for reactive power:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{If, } Q_{ref} - Q \geq HB Q \quad dQ = 1 \\ \text{If, } Q_{ref} - Q < HB Q \quad dQ = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

However, the optimal switching states of the converter can be uniquely determined at any specific moment based on the combination of input signals, utilizing Table 3.

Table 3.VSI switching sectors

DP	DQ	SECTOR	VECTOR	SECTOR	VECTOR
1	0	S1	V6	S2	V7
	1		V7		V7
0	V6		V1		
1	V1		V2		
1	0	S3	V1	S4	V1
	1		V0		V0
0	V1		V2		
1	V2		V3		
1	0	S5	V2	S6	V7
	1		V7		V7
0	V2		V3		
1	V3		V4		
1	0	S7	V3	S8	V0
	1		V0		V0
0	V3		V4		
1	V4		V5		
1	0	S9	V4	S10	V7
	1		V7		V7
0	V4		V5		
1	V5		V6		
1	0	S11	V5	S12	V0
	1		V0		V0
0	V5		V6		
1	V6		V1		

4. Simulation results

In this section, the results of the simulations are presented and analysed in order to assess the performance of the structure studied and the effectiveness of the control strategies implemented. To do this, a five (5) second simulation was carried out under a two-level irradiation profile: 600 W/m² between 0 and 2 seconds, then 1000 W/m², as shown in Figure 8. In addition, a non-linear load variation occurred from the fourth second onwards. The results show that, despite these disturbances, the output voltage of the boost converter remains well regulated around the reference value of 380 V, as shown in Figure 9. Figure 10 also shows the evolution of the position and the passage through the twelve (12) sectors, in perfect accordance with the Direct Power Control (DPC) strategy. By using this control, a current is injected at the point of connection to the grid (see Figure 11), thereby compensating for the harmonics generated by the non-linear load and preventing them from being fed back into the grid.

The same figure also provides zoomed-in views of different parts of the signal. Figure 12 also shows the superposition of the voltage and current signals for phase A, with three explanatory zooms. Note that the current has been multiplied by a factor of 40 to make the curves easier to read.

Finally, a second series of figures (14 and 15) shows the analysis of the rate of harmonic distortion (THD) of the network currents, for the cases with and without an active filter. Without the filter, the

currents are highly distorted, with THD levels of 18.24% and 20.40% respectively, well in excess of standards. On the other hand, with the active filter connected, THD levels are considerably reduced, reaching a maximum of 4.14%, which is still in line with international power quality standards.

Fig 8. Profil of irradiation

Figure 9. V_{dc_ref} and V_{dc} measured

Fig 10. Position and Sectors

Fig 11. Injected current of filter

Fig 12. Voltage and Current grid

Fig 13. Active and reactive power

Fig14. THD without control DSP

Fig15. THD with control DSP

5. Conclusion

The work presented in this article has made it possible to validate the effectiveness of the direct power control strategy developed, through simulations carried out in the MATLAB/Simulink environment. The results confirm the system's ability to optimally inject the active power from the photovoltaic source while ensuring effective compensation of the reactive power. In addition, a significant improvement in power quality was observed, with a significant reduction in the rate of harmonic distortion (THD) of the source current. These performances attest to the relevance of the proposed strategy for energy conversion applications in smart grid-connected electrical systems.

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